

Using an embedded researcher and coproduction approach to mobilise research into policy and practice: findings from an evaluation of an integrated homelessness service in Doncaster, UK

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Background:

Homelessness is a global health and policy issue with detrimental impacts on individual health and wellbeing and wider healthcare systems. Increased policy attention has highlighted the need for multiagency working to prevent homelessness. Here we present findings of an evaluation of an integrated housing/health service in Doncaster, UK. The service aims to support individuals with multiple complex needs to access services and prevent ongoing homelessness.

Methods:

The evaluation adopted a mixed-methods design underpinned by a coproduction and action research approach. The study utilised semi-structured interviews with clients (=9) and professionals within the service and the wider housing/health system (N=17), 30+ hours of observation data from operational and strategic meetings and analysis of routine service data (N=97). Two workshops were undertaken with operational and strategic partners to sense check findings, coproduce recommendations and create action plans to mobilise knowledge into practice. The use of an embedded researcher model facilitated coproduction and knowledge translation.

Results:

The service supported clients to maintain stable accommodation through facilitating access to vital services such as dentists, GPs, addiction services and debt and money management support. Key to the success of the service was its person centred and flexible approach which tailored support to individual need. Challenges included barriers to accessing the health system, a lack of suitable accommodation, difficulties in multidisciplinary working and perceived stigma from council and health services. Recommendations included the need for greater engagement from health and strategic partners to facilitate policy change. Findings from the evaluation will have relevance for the delivery of integrated services to reduce homelessness in other areas.

Conclusions:

Individuals need support with the wider determinants of homelessness to enable them to sustain stable accommodation. The service is an important part of the system but requires buy in and engagement with other services for successful implementation.